

PROSPECTS FOR US DIGITAL DIPLOMACY IN CENTRAL ASIA

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The future prospects of the US digital diplomacy in Central Asia depend on the foreign policy towards the region and the political environment in Central Asia. Today, the US is in a good position to conduct digital diplomacy. In particular, the following favorable situation in Central Asia can be noted as an example:

- The number of users of the Internet and social networks among the population of the Central Asian region is increasing;
- infrastructure for mass media and Internet networks;
- the fact that the Internet and social networks are becoming the main source of information on various issues for those working in state bodies and ordinary citizens;
- in recent years, the opinions of bloggers and social network users are becoming more influential in the government's decision-making.

The increase of Internet users among the population in the Central Asian region is related to the following: 1) penetration of the Internet infrastructure into all populated areas; 2) Internet quality is improving; 3) decrease in the price of Internet connection; 4) The need for residents to receive daily information, watch various videos, and receive and send business-related information via the Internet. In addition, the development of the digital economy by countries and the use of digital diplomacy in their foreign policy is also related to the Internet.

The newest document describing the foreign political relations of the USA with the region in the following years is the report of the US State Department. This report is the U.S. Strategy for Central Asia 2019-2025: Promoting Sovereignty and Economic Development, published by the US State Department's Bureau of South and Central Asia in February 2019.

Based on this strategy, we can see the perspective of US digital diplomacy in Central Asia in the following areas:

First of all, the digital diplomacy of the United States will be to help strengthen and develop cooperation in various fields with the countries of Central Asia as a bilateral and integrated region. An example of this is the analysis of the mechanism and means of digital diplomacy of the USA in the

region, including the official website of the diplomatic institution, pages on social networks and other Internet sources.

Over the past 1 year (from January 2023 to January 2024), the official website of the United States in Uzbekistan has provided more than 80 news, which are mainly about the cooperation and projects of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) with Uzbekistan. and aids. For example, USAID's innovative initiative to promote sustainable and inclusive economic growth, a new initiative to support Uzbekistan's clean energy goals, USAID's five-year All Children Succeed project, USAID's Agribusiness Development Project, and prestigious rankings and indexes of organizations Reports on Uzbekistan are dedicated to civil society support in Uzbekistan and other issues.

Other countries in the region, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, have similar official websites and social media news. According to this news, one of the main goals of the US digital diplomacy is to improve its positive image in the region, to show the positive aspects of cooperation in various fields for the region, and to present it as a state that provides material support.

These trends indicate that in the future, the prospects of digital diplomacy of the United States will focus more on this direction. The growth of US digital diplomacy in the coverage of the above topics on official websites, social networks and other Internet sources also shows its perspective.

Also, the USA aims to strengthen large-scale projects to strengthen relations with the region. In particular, one of such projects is the C5+1 project. In particular, on January 7, 2021, a joint statement on Central Asian investment cooperation was published on the official website of the US embassies in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. According to it, the governments of the USA, the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Republic of Uzbekistan announced the establishment of the Central Asian investment partnership. In order to support the projects, they will use all available efforts to invest at least one billion dollars for five years.

US Secretary of State Anthony Blinken strongly supports the sovereignty, independence and territorial integrity of the Central Asian countries through the Internet and social networks, and emphasized the importance of regional cooperation in the C5+1 format for the peoples and the practical support of the US in ensuring regional security. appeals are made regarding the means and place of cooperation.

As a general conclusion, the issue of regional security of Central Asia has occupied an important place in the foreign policy of the USA. This issue remains relevant in the future tasks and directions of digital diplomacy of the USA.

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